

Transannular Electronic Interaction of 1, 6-Cyclodecanedithione and Its Synthesis

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An interesting ten-membered medium-sized ring compound, 1, 6-cyclodecanedithione, is prepared and its ultraviolet absorption spectra in carbon tetrachloride, tetrahydrofuran and chloroform are studied. The compound exhibits unusual absorption bands at the wavelengths of 265 nm, 275 nm and 310 nm and have the molar absorptivities of 2657, 890 and 640 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in carbon tetrachloride, tetrahydrofuran and chloroform respectively. The presence of a strong absorption band at 265 nm region is taken as evidence for this transannular electronic interaction in the excited state. The origin of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition (K-band) and its assignment are discussed from the standpoint of the transannular electronic interaction (Transannular Conjugation)¹. This is an interesting consequence of the stereochemistry of the ten-membered ring.

BY using naphthalene as starting material, a medium-sized ring compound, 1, 6-cyclodecanedione I, was prepared². The dione I was next converted to 1, 6-cyclodecanedithione II by reacting it with phosphorus pentasulfide (Fig. 1). Some ketones have been changed to thioketones by the action of phosphorus pentasulfide³.

Fig. 1. Synthesis of 1, 6-Cyclodecanedithione

Sulfur and oxygen are both members of group IV of the periodic table. They have similar outer shell configuration and their chemistry is similar in part. Any differences in chemical behaviour may usually be attributed to the facts that sulfur is larger, less electronegative and has occupied 3p orbitals which are larger and higher in energy levels.

In contrast to oxygen, sulfur enters into p-p π bonding reluctantly when the reaction is forced upon it. The reasons for this reluctance of 3p orbitals to form π bonds are that the bonds are quite long, so that 3p overlap is not very effective. In the case of C=S group, the 2p-2p π bond, the 3p orbital occurs in such a way as to decrease the net effective overlap of the two orbitals. Therefore the 2p-3p π bond is weaker than the 2p-2p π bond. Thus thiocarbonyl compounds, in which the π bond of the C=S grouping is formed from overlap of the carbon 2p and sulfur 3p orbitals, are less stable than the

corresponding carbonyl compounds and therefore easy to polarize with increase in solvent polarity.

The thiocarbonyl (C=S) group contains, in addition to a pair of σ electrons, a pair of π -electrons and two pairs of nonbonding (n or p) electrons on sulfur. The thioketones can give rise to two types of absorption bands, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The short wavelength band is intense and arises from a $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The longer wavelength band is weak and arises from a $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition.

Transannular Interaction :

The ultraviolet and visible spectra of 1, 6-cyclodecanedithione have been measured in carbon tetrachloride and the compound exhibits an unusual absorption band at 265 nm with a molar absorptivity of 2657 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Similar bands have been observed in the spectra of other cyclic systems containing nonconjugated chromophores and have been attributed to transannular electronic interactions^{2, 4, 5}. The presence of a strong absorption band in the 265 nm region is taken as evidence for this transannular electronic interaction in the excited state.

In the case of 1, 6-cyclodecanedithione, because of the flexibility and puckering of the ring, the nonconjugated two C=S chromophores can come closer to each other and assume a S-cis-butadiene type conjugation. This permits the orientation of the p-orbitals of the carbon and sulfur to be oriented parallel to each other and thus permit and effective overlap of the π -orbitals of the two C=S

chromophores (Fig. 2). This has been confirmed by the model construction. Such an orbital overlap gives rise to bonding and antibonding π -molecular orbitals which encompass both the chromophores.

Fig. 2. π -Orbital Parallel Overlap.

Effect of Solvent Polarity :

In nonpolar solvent, carbon tetrachloride, the absorption band for two C=S chromophores of 1,6-cyclodecanedithione appears at 265 nm region. The 265 nm band can then be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition (K-band). The strong K-band ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition), $\epsilon_m = 2675$, probably submerges the weak R-band ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition).

When the spectra of 1,6-cyclodecanedithione was determined in tetrahydrofuran the absorption band appeared at the longer wavelength at 275 nm with molar absorptivity 890 liter mole⁻¹cm⁻¹. This absorption involves $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the C=S chromophores and undergoes a bathochromic shift (a red shift) as solvent polarity is increased. The red shift presumably results from a reduction in the energy level of the excited state accompanying dipole-dipole interaction. The weak absorption near 308 nm appears as a shoulder due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition (Table 1).

And when the spectra of 1,6-cyclodecanedithione was determined in chloroform the absorption band appeared at 310 nm with molar absorptivity 640 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. This absorption involves an $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the C=S chromophores and undergoes a bathochromic shift as the solvent polarity is increased. The weak R-band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition probably submerged under K-band due to the hypsochromic shift (a blue shift) of absorption to a shorter wavelength due to strong solvent effect.

Since thiocarbonyl compounds are polar, the positions of the K-bands and R-bands are both dependent on the solvent polarity. The K-bands ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions) of thioketones undergo a batho-

chromic shift (a red shift) and hypochromic effect with increasing solvent polarity. And R-bands ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions) of thioketones undergo a hypsochromic shift (a blue shift) as the polarity of the solvent is increased (Table I).

TABLE—1 EFFECT OF SOLVENT POLARITY ON THE SPECTRUM OF 1,6-CYCLODECANEDITHIONE

Solvent	Transition	
	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ (λ_m , nm)	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$ (λ_m , nm)
Carbon tetrachloride	265	—
Tetrahydrofuran	275	308
Chloroform	310	Submerged under K-band

Similar effects of solvent polarity on the ultraviolet absorption spectra of mesityl oxide in isooctane, chloroform and water are observed⁶.

Degree of Transannular Interactions :

Four medium-sized ring compounds, 1,6-cyclodecanedione I, 1,6-dimethylenecyclodecane IV, 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime III and 1,6-cyclodecanedithione II have been synthesized and have been examined for evidence of C=O, C=C, C=N and C=S transannular interactions. These compounds I, II, III and IV exhibit different degrees of transannular interactions. 1,6-cyclodecanedione shows $\lambda_m = 287$ nm and $\epsilon = 35$; 1,6-dimethylenecyclodecane shows $\lambda_m = 256$ nm and $\epsilon = 500$; cyclodecanedione dioxime shows $\lambda_m = 246$ nm and $\epsilon = 13,200$;

TABLE—2 COMPARISON OF SPECTRAL DATA FOR 1,6-CYCLODECANEDITHIONE AND RELATED COMPOUNDS

Compound	Solvent	λ_m , nm	ϵ_m
1,6-Cyclodecanedithione	Carbon tetrachloride	265	2,675
1,6-Dimethylenecyclodecane ^a	Ethanol	256	500
1,6-Cyclodecanedione Dioxime ^b	Ethanol	246	13,200
1,6-Cyclodecanedione ^c	Ethanol	287	35
Cyclodec-5-en-1-one ^d	Ethanol	258	472
1-Methyl-1-azacyclodecan-6-one ^e	Diethyl ether	221	5,600
1-Thiacyclooctan-5-one ^f	Carbon tetrachloride	238	2,535
1,5-Dithiacyclooctane ^g	Ethanol	202	3,000

and 1,6-cyclodecanedithione shows $\lambda_m=265$ nm and $\epsilon=2675$ (Table 2).

These compounds are chosen first because of the favourable geometry for such interactions of the ten-membered ring with diametrically opposed two similar functional groups and second to check the predicted correlation of the interactions of $C=N>C=S>C=C>C=O$ order in the magnitude of the resulting ultraviolet absorption (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Transannular Interactions $C=N>C=S>C=C>C=O$

Transannular Interactions in Other Sulfur Compounds⁴

Ultraviolet maxima of 1-thiacyclodecan-5-one V have been determined in carbon tetrachloride and the compound showed an unusual absorption band at 238 nm with a molar absorptivity of 2,565 liter/mole⁴/cm (Fig. 4). The interaction, in apparently nonconjugated system, is due to an effective overlap of the π -orbitals of the $C=O$ group and the p (or n) orbitals of the sulfur⁴ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Transannular Interactions in Related Sulfur Compounds.

Similar effects are observed when there can be effective overlap of the p (or n) orbitals of the two sulfur atoms across the ring of 1,5-dithiacyclooctane VI which showed strong absorption near 202 nm with molar absorptivity 300 liter/mole/cm⁴ (Fig. 4).

Experimental

1, 6-Cyclodecanedithione II :

Phosphorus pentasulfide (20 g) was dissolved in

100 ml carbon disulfide in a three-necked flask equipped with water condenser, separatory funnel and nitrogen inert atmosphere. Cyclodecanedione I (10 g) was dissolved in 100 ml carbon disulfide in a separatory funnel. The solution of cyclodecanedione was added slowly through separatory funnel to the solution of phosphorus pentasulfide. The reaction mixture was stirred under nitrogen atmosphere for seventy-two hours. Then water was added drop by drop to destroy the remaining phosphorus pentasulfide. The reaction mixture was poured into 1000 ml separatory funnel and the compound was extracted with carbon disulfide. The combined carbon disulfide extracts were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulfate overnight. It was filtered and the solvent was removed from the filtrate by rotary evaporator. The solid compound was recrystallized from carbon disulfide and was dried in vacuum oven. The yield was 80%.

The compound, 1,6-cyclodecanedithione, is insoluble in most of the organic solvents except carbon tetrachloride, tetrahydrofuran, chloroform and carbon disulfide. The melting point of the compound is 118° and is uncorrected. The infra-red absorption, for thiocarbonyl group ($C=S$) stretching frequencies, gives two sharp peaks at 1250 cm^{-1} and 1070 cm^{-1} . This is consistent with $C=S$ absorption in thiourea and thiobenzophenone⁹. Ultra violet absorption spectra of the compound are at 265 nm in carbon tetrachloride; 275 nm in tetrahydrofuran; and 310 nm in chloroform. Carbon, sulfur and hydrogen analysis, calculated for $C_{10}S_2H_{16}$: C, 60%; S, 32%; H, 8%. Found: C, 60.08%; S, 31.91%; H, 8.05%.

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